

ChatGPT-4.5 versus pharmacists in OTC counseling: A bilingual comparative study

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Abstract

Background: Over-the-counter (OTC) medications enable self-care but require accurate counseling to prevent misuse, particularly in multilingual settings with limited health literacy. Pharmacists provide expert guidance; however, time constraints hinder comprehensive interactions. Generative artificial intelligence (AI) models such as ChatGPT-4.5 offer potential as decision-support tools, but their performance compared with pharmacists in bilingual OTC counseling remains underexplored. This study compared ChatGPT-4.5 and community pharmacists using standardized gastrointestinal case scenarios in English and Arabic to assess response quality, safety, and appropriateness.

Methods: This cross-sectional study evaluated 22 standardized OTC cases (e.g., constipation, diarrhea) from authoritative sources, presented in English and Arabic. Fifty-eight Jordanian community pharmacists ($n = 29$ per language) solved five cases each. All 44 AI responses were generated via standardized prompts without iteration. Responses were blindly rated by four experts using the CLEAR framework (completeness, lack of false information, evidence-based, appropriateness, and relevance; 5-point Likert scale). Cosine similarity quantified textual overlap; Welch's t -tests, ANOVA, and correlations analyzed differences (SPSS v.29; $\alpha = 0.05$). Inter-rater reliability was assessed using ICC.

Results: ChatGPT-4.5 achieved higher mean CLEAR scores (4.8/5) than pharmacists (3.7–3.8/5; $p < 0.001$) across languages and domains, with no language differences ($p > 0.05$). AI excelled in completeness and lack of false information; pharmacist performance declined with case difficulty. Cosine similarity was low (0.04–0.11), indicating distinct yet coherent AI phrasing. Younger pharmacists scored higher ($r = -0.33$, $p = 0.01$). Qualitative analysis showed more consistent structure in AI-generated responses and greater variability among pharmacists.

Conclusion: ChatGPT-4.5 demonstrates robust, language-agnostic performance for OTC counseling, suggesting its role as an educational benchmark and clinical adjunct to standardize advice and reduce variability. Pharmacy curricula should integrate AI literacy and targeted training in red-flag recognition to enhance human–AI synergy, fostering safer patient outcomes and interprofessional collaboration.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, bilingual assessment, ChatGPT-4.5, CLEAR framework, community pharmacists, over-the-counter counseling, pharmacy education

Introduction

Over-the-counter (OTC) or non-prescription drugs represent a cornerstone of modern self-care, allowing patients to manage minor ailments without physician consultation. They are widely used for pain, allergies, gastrointestinal discomfort, and cold symptoms, and they offer cost-effective and rapid access to relief. However, their safe and effective use depends on accurate self-diagnosis, correct product selection, and adherence to dosing instructions. Without professional guidance, inappropriate self-medication can lead to drug interactions, masking of serious diseases, or toxic overdoses, particularly in populations with limited health literacy or polypharmacy exposure (Becker et al. 2023; Fendrick et al. 2008).

Pharmacists serve as the primary frontline healthcare professionals, ensuring the safe and effective use of OTC medications. Their expertise enables the evaluation of presenting symptoms, differentiation of self-limiting from serious conditions, and provision of evidence-based recommendations (Jairoun et al. 2022; Mujtaba and Gazerani 2024). Through patient counseling, pharmacists bridge the gap between consumer autonomy and medical supervision, improving therapeutic outcomes and minimizing medication misuse. Nevertheless, growing demands on pharmacy services, workforce shortages, and time constraints often limit the depth of counseling provided, especially in busy community settings (White et al. 2025).

Recently, artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force in healthcare delivery. Among its most advanced applications are generative AI models such as ChatGPT-4.5, which utilize large-scale neural networks and reinforcement learning with human feedback to generate coherent, context-aware, and evidence-based responses to textual queries (Ray 2023; Reddy 2024). These models have shown promise in diverse clinical domains, including drug information provision, medical education, and diagnostic support (Tu et al. 2025). Their ability to rapidly synthesize data from extensive medical literature suggests that they may have potential as decision-support tools in pharmacy practice—particularly for routine counseling and non-prescription drug management.

Early evaluations indicate that ChatGPT can produce accurate and well-structured therapeutic recommendations, yet its ability to emulate the contextual reasoning, ethical sensitivity, and individualized judgment of pharmacists remains uncertain (Alsanosi and Padmanabhan 2024; Huang et al. 2024). While generative AI excels at structured, data-driven tasks such as identifying drug–drug interactions, it may underperform when faced with

ambiguous patient presentations or incomplete histories—scenarios frequently encountered in real-world community pharmacy. Furthermore, most prior research has focused on English-language interactions, leaving the performance of generative AI in multilingual environments largely unexplored.

Assessing how AI compares with pharmacists in solving OTC case scenarios is therefore of both scientific and practical importance. Reliable benchmarking can inform whether AI tools can augment pharmacy services, improve patient access to high-quality information, or pose risks if used without professional oversight. This study sought to address these gaps by systematically comparing the quality, safety, and contextual appropriateness of responses generated by ChatGPT-4.5 and licensed community pharmacists when solving standardized OTC case scenarios presented in both English and Arabic.

By employing the validated CLEAR framework—assessing Completeness, Lack of false information, Evidence-based reasoning, Appropriateness, and Relevance—along with cosine similarity and statistical validation, this work aims to provide the first comprehensive evaluation of generative AI versus human pharmacists in OTC counseling across bilingual contexts. The findings will elucidate whether ChatGPT-4.5 can serve as a reliable adjunct to human expertise, identify areas requiring algorithmic refinement, and guide the ethical integration of AI into pharmacy practice.

Methods

Study design

A cross-sectional comparative study was conducted to evaluate and contrast the quality of responses generated by ChatGPT-4.5 and licensed community pharmacists in solving OTC drug case scenarios. Twenty-two standardized cases were selected from authoritative references, including the *Handbook of Nonprescription Drugs*, *Managing Symptoms in the Pharmacy*, and *Community Pharmacy: Symptoms, Diagnosis and Treatment*. Gastrointestinal OTC conditions were intentionally selected because they are among the most frequent symptom-based presentations encountered in community pharmacy practice, often require rapid triage between self-care and medical referral, and are associated with meaningful safety risks when red flags are missed (Frieling et al. 2023; Merks et al. 2026). In addition, these conditions are well represented in standard nonprescription

therapeutic references, allowing the use of structured and standardized scenarios suitable for direct benchmarking (De Busser et al. 2025; ZainAlAbdin et al. 2026). The selected cases covered six gastrointestinal conditions commonly encountered in community practice: constipation, diarrhea, hemorrhoids, nausea and vomiting, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), and mouth ulcers. Each case was presented in both English and Arabic, allowing a direct bilingual comparison.

Because each pharmacist completed five case scenarios, the pharmacist dataset had a repeated-measures structure, with responses nested within participants. The study was primarily designed as a comparative cross-sectional evaluation of response quality between human- and AI-generated answers rather than as a longitudinal or hierarchical modeling study. Accordingly, the main inferential analyses were planned using summary comparisons, and this design feature was considered during interpretation of the findings.

Participants

A total of 58 licensed community pharmacists practicing in Amman, Jordan, were recruited through balanced convenience sampling to ensure balanced representation between East and West Amman. The sample size was determined *a priori* using a power analysis for an independent-samples comparison between two groups (English vs. Arabic). Assuming a medium effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.5$), a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, and a desired power of 0.8, the minimum required sample was 52 participants. Participants were randomly assigned to answer five case scenarios in either English or Arabic (29 per group). The study relied on self-reported comfort with both languages at enrollment and did not administer a formal language-proficiency test.

Inclusion criteria required active practice in community pharmacy and willingness to provide written responses. Participation was voluntary, and informed oral consent was obtained before participation. Written consent was unnecessary because the study was anonymous, minimal risk, and involved no personal identifiers. Similar community-pharmacy surveys have used oral or implied consent under comparable conditions (Rodgers et al. 2016; Zeidan et al. 2019; Patterson et al. 2022).

ChatGPT-4.5 Arm

All 22 case scenarios were submitted to ChatGPT-4.5 in both English and Arabic using standardized prompts. The English prompt read, "You are a licensed community pharmacist. Provide a brief, evidence-based answer to the following questions," while the Arabic equivalent was phrased as "أنت صيدلاني مجاز في صيدلية مجتمعية، أجب بإيجاز وبأسلوب علمي "مبني على الدليل على الأسئلة التالية". No iterative prompting or clarification was allowed to simulate typical end-user interaction. A total of 44 AI-generated responses (22 per language) were collected for evaluation.

Difficulty index classification

Prior to data collection, a pilot group of five pharmacists solved all cases to provide a preliminary estimate of case difficulty using a structured rubric derived from educational assessment methods. Responses were graded from 0.0 (incorrect/unsafe) to 1.0 (fully correct or appropriate referral). The Difficulty Index (DI) for each case was calculated as the mean pilot score and used as an internal, exploratory classification to stratify cases as Easy (DI > 0.8), *Moderate* (0.4–0.8), or *Difficult* (DI < 0.4). Because this classification was based on a small pilot sample, it should be interpreted as approximate rather than a formally validated measure of case difficulty.

Evaluation framework

All pharmacist and ChatGPT-4.5 responses were evaluated using the CLEAR (Criteria for Language and Evidence-based Assessment of Responses) framework, initially developed and piloted by Sallam et al. (2023) to assess health information quality generated by AI. The CLEAR framework was considered suitable for this study because it evaluates key dimensions directly relevant to OTC counseling quality, including completeness, factual accuracy, evidence basis, appropriateness, and scenario relevance. It was also appropriate for bilingual comparison because scoring emphasized clinical meaning and contextual fit rather than language form alone.

Four pharmacists with postgraduate training and expertise in drug information independently served as raters. Each response was assessed using the five domains of the CLEAR framework: completeness, lack of false information, evidence-based, appropriateness, and relevance. Each domain was scored on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = very poor to 5 = excellent). A composite CLEAR score was calculated for every response by averaging across the five domains.

Prior to evaluation, all raters participated in a calibration session using sample cases to ensure consistent interpretation of scoring criteria. To confirm scoring consistency, inter-rater reliability was assessed using the Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) based on a two-way random-effects model with absolute agreement. Both single-measures (ICC[2,1]) and average-measures (ICC[2,4]) were reported, representing the reliability of individual raters and pooled ratings, respectively. All evaluators were blinded to the source of each response (pharmacist or ChatGPT-4.5) to minimize bias and ensure objective assessment.

Interpretation of ICC values followed the thresholds presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Interpretation thresholds for Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) reliability (Koo and Li 2016).

ICC value range	Interpretation
< 0.50	Poor reliability
0.50–0.75	Moderate reliability
0.75–0.90	Good reliability
> 0.90	Excellent reliability

Textual similarity analysis

To quantify linguistic resemblance between ChatGPT-4.5 and pharmacists' responses, cosine similarity was calculated after preprocessing texts (tokenization, stop-word removal, and TF-IDF vectorization). Scores ranged from 0 (no similarity) to 1 (identical text).

Statistical analysis

All analyses were performed using SPSS v.29 (IBM, NY, USA). Data were summarized as mean \pm SD for continuous variables and frequencies (%) for categorical variables. Group comparisons between ChatGPT-4.5 and pharmacists were conducted using Welch's *t*-test or paired-sample *t*-test where appropriate. Associations between demographic factors and CLEAR scores were explored using Pearson's correlation, independent *t*-tests, or one-way ANOVA. Correlations between CLEAR and cosine similarity were analyzed using Pearson's *r*, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Since each pharmacist contributed five responses, response-level observations were not fully independent. For the main pharmacist-versus-ChatGPT analyses, response-level data were used to preserve case-specific information; however, pharmacist performance was also examined at the participant level by averaging CLEAR scores across the five cases answered by each pharmacist. Because the participant-level patterns were comparable to the response-level findings, the primary analyses were retained as presented. Formal multilevel or cluster-adjusted models were not applied, and this should be considered when interpreting *p*-values and precision estimates.

Results

Demographic and practice characteristics

Fifty-eight licensed community pharmacists participated, split evenly by language (Arabic 29; English 29) and location (East Amman 29; West Amman 29). Shift distribution was A 48.3% ($n = 28$), B 41.4% ($n = 24$), and C 10.3% ($n = 6$). Most worked in independent pharmacies (77.6%, $n = 45$). Age groups were ≤ 25 years, 34.5% ($n = 20$); 26–35 years, 50.0% ($n = 29$); > 35 years, 15.5% ($n = 9$), with a mean of 29.5 years (range 22–55). Time to solve cases: ≤ 5 min 36.2% ($n = 21$), 6–10 min 46.6% ($n = 27$), and > 10 min 17.2% ($n = 10$), with a mean of 7.8 min (range 3–20) (Table 2).

Cosine similarity and CLEAR scores across languages

Across both languages, ChatGPT-4.5 responses achieved significantly higher CLEAR scores than pharmacists (all $p < 0.001$). Cosine similarity (pharmacist vs. ChatGPT-4.5) was higher in English than in Arabic ($p < 0.001$). Cosine similarity values between pharmacist and ChatGPT-4.5

Table 2. Demographic and practice characteristics of participating pharmacists.

Characteristic	Category	Number of pharmacists	Percentage (%)
Language	Arabic	29	50.0%
	English	29	50.0%
Shift time*	A	28	48.3%
	B	24	41.4%
	C	6	10.3%
Location	East Amman	29	50.0%
	West Amman	29	50.0%
Pharmacy type	Individual	45	77.6%
	Chain	13	22.4%
Age (years)	≤ 25	20	34.5%
	26–35	29	50.0%
	> 35	9	15.5%
	Mean (SD)	29.5 (6.8)	-
Time to solve (min)	≤ 5	21	36.2%
	6–10	27	46.6%
	> 10	10	17.2%
	Mean (SD)	7.8 (3.7)	-

*Shift time represents different work shifts (A = morning, B = afternoon (evening), C = night).

responses were generally low (mean 0.04–0.11), indicating that ChatGPT-4.5's answers were linguistically distinct rather than textually overlapping with those of pharmacists. This low lexical similarity does not reflect reduced clinical relevance; instead, it suggests that ChatGPT-4.5 produced independently constructed yet clinically coherent recommendations. In practical terms, ChatGPT-4.5 generated alternative phrasing and structure while maintaining therapeutic accuracy, which may be advantageous for patient comprehension and stylistic diversity. No significant differences were detected between languages for pharmacist CLEAR ($p = 0.277$) or ChatGPT-4.5 CLEAR ($p = 0.834$) (Table 3).

Performance across CLEAR components

ChatGPT-4.5 outperformed pharmacists in all five CLEAR dimensions in both languages (all $p < 0.0001$).

The largest gaps appeared for lack of false information and completeness; relevance was the strongest domain for both groups (Table 4).

Association of demographics with pharmacist CLEAR scores

At the pharmacist level ($n = 58$), CLEAR scores did not differ by language ($t = -0.89$, $p = 0.38$), pharmacy type ($t = 0.44$, $p = 0.66$), or shift ($F = 0.99$, $p = 0.38$). A

Table 3. Comparison of cosine similarity and CLEAR scores between pharmacists and ChatGPT-4.5 responses in English and Arabic.

Language	Cosine similarity (mean ± SD, n)	Pharmacists CLEAR (mean ± SD, n)	ChatGPT-4.5 CLEAR (mean ± SD, n)	p-value (pharmacists vs. ChatGPT-4.5)
Arabic	0.04 ± 0.04 (n = 145)	3.68 ± 0.95 (n = 145)	4.78 ± 0.32 (n = 22 cases)	< 0.001
English	0.11 ± 0.12 (n = 145)	3.79 ± 0.76 (n = 145)	4.80 ± 0.31 (n = 22 cases)	< 0.001
Both	0.08 ± 0.08 (n = 290)	3.74 ± 0.85 (n = 290)	4.77 ± 0.32 (n = 44)	< 0.001
p-value (Arabic vs. English)	<0.001	0.277	0.834	-

Note: The number of pharmacist responses ($n = 145$ per language) reflects 29 pharmacists \times 5 cases; $n = 22$ cases per language for ChatGPT-4.5, which represents 22 unique case numbers evaluated in each language (44 total). p -values are calculated using Welch's t -test for unequal variances, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

trend suggested higher scores in East vs. West Amman ($t = 1.82$, $p = 0.07$). Age was inversely associated with CLEAR ($r = -0.33$, $p = 0.01$); each year corresponded to

a -0.0235 change in score (95% CI -0.0415 to -0.0054 ; $R^2 = 0.108$). Time to solve showed no association ($r = -0.05$, $p = 0.69$) (Table 5).

Table 4. Pharmacists vs. ChatGPT-4.5 on CLEAR components.

CLEAR-components	Group	Pharmacists (mean ± SD)	ChatGPT-4.5 (mean ± SD)	p-value
Completeness	English	3.60 ± 0.41	4.68 ± 0.48	< 0.0001
	Arabic	3.54 ± 0.66	4.64 ± 0.45	< 0.0001
Lack of false	English	3.88 ± 0.42	4.82 ± 0.21	< 0.0001
	Arabic	3.76 ± 0.58	4.86 ± 0.23	< 0.0001
Evidence-based	English	3.72 ± 0.43	4.78 ± 0.33	< 0.0001
	Arabic	3.54 ± 0.60	4.74 ± 0.33	< 0.0001
Appropriateness	English	3.65 ± 0.42	4.69 ± 0.52	< 0.0001
	Arabic	3.49 ± 0.58	4.64 ± 0.50	< 0.0001
Relevance	English	4.17 ± 0.33	4.93 ± 0.22	< 0.0001
	Arabic	4.05 ± 0.61	4.93 ± 0.22	< 0.0001

Note. Values are presented as mean ± SD. Pharmacist scores represent the average per pharmacist ($n = 29$ per language group). ChatGPT-4.5 scores represent average performance across 22 case scenarios per language group. p -values are based on independent-samples Welch's t -tests.

Case-type comparisons

By case category, ChatGPT-4.5 scored significantly higher than pharmacists in nearly all comparisons for both languages. English: significant gaps for constipation, diarrhea, hemorrhoids, N/V, and GERD; mouth ulcers did not reach significance. Arabic: significant gaps for constipation, diarrhea, hemorrhoids, N/V, and GERD; mouth ulcers were not significant (Tables 6, 7).

Correlation between cosine similarity and CLEAR

For ChatGPT-4.5, cosine similarity showed weak, non-significant positive correlations with CLEAR for both English ($r = 0.236$, $p = 0.329$) and Arabic ($r = 0.240$, $p = 0.283$). For pharmacists (response-level), the correlation was moderate and significant in English

Table 5. Association between demographic variables and average CLEAR scores ($n = 58$).

Demographic variable	Test used	Key statistics	Interpretation
Language (Arabic vs. English)	t -test	$t = -0.89$, $p = 0.38$	No significant difference. Language of cases not related to CLEAR scores.
Shift time (A vs. B vs. C)	ANOVA	$F = 0.99$, $p = 0.38$	No significant differences across shifts.
Location (East Amman vs. West Amman)	t -test	$t = 1.82$, $p = 0.07$	Marginal difference ($p < 0.10$). Pharmacists in East Amman tended to have higher scores.
Pharmacy type (individual vs. chain)	t -test	$t = 0.44$, $p = 0.66$	No significant difference. Pharmacy type not related to CLEAR.
Age	Pearson correlation	$r = -0.33$, $p = 0.01$	Significant negative correlation. Older pharmacists had lower scores.
Time to solve	Pearson correlation	$r = -0.05$, $p = 0.69$	No significant correlation. Response speed not related to performance.

Table 6. Comparison of cosine similarity and CLEAR scores by case type (English)*.

Case type	Cosine mean ± SD	Pharmacists CLEAR mean ± SD	ChatGPT-4.5 CLEAR mean ± SD	p-value (pharmacists vs. ChatGPT-4.5)
Constipation	0.126 ± 0.147	3.89 ± 0.76	4.74 ± 0.24	< 0.001
Diarrhea	0.104 ± 0.123	3.63 ± 0.69	4.9 ± 0.11	< 0.001
Hemorrhoids	0.115 ± 0.101	3.95 ± 0.61	4.74 ± 0.43	0.023
Nausea and vomiting	0.147 ± 0.126	4.44 ± 0.77	5.0 ± 0.0	0.037
GERD	0.029 ± 0.032	3.64 ± 0.77	4.88 ± 0.16	< 0.001
Mouth ulcer	0.072 ± 0.056	3.09 ± 0.78	4.43 ± 0.58	0.113

*Note. Number of cases total, $n = 145$, reflects 29 pharmacists \times 5 cases; $n = 22$ for ChatGPT-4.5 reflects 22 unique case numbers evaluated. p -values are calculated using Welch's t -test for unequal variances, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 7. Comparison of cosine similarity and CLEAR scores by case type (Arabic)*.

Case type	Cosine mean \pm SD	Pharmacists CLEAR mean \pm SD	ChatGPT-4.5 CLEAR mean \pm SD	<i>p</i> -value (pharmacists vs. ChatGPT-4.5)
Constipation	0.035 \pm 0.033	3.45 \pm 1.03	4.7 \pm 0.19	< 0.001
Diarrhea	0.037 \pm 0.035	3.74 \pm 0.91	4.86 \pm 0.09	< 0.001
Hemorrhoids	0.043 \pm 0.038	3.64 \pm 0.80	4.66 \pm 0.45	0.011
Nausea and vomiting	0.045 \pm 0.048	3.85 \pm 1.02	4.98 \pm 0.03	< 0.001
GERD	0.029 \pm 0.031	3.85 \pm 0.62	4.85 \pm 0.21	< 0.001
Mouth ulcer	0.050 \pm 0.039	3.7 \pm 1.26	4.43 \pm 0.48	0.2079

*Note. Number of cases total, $n = 145$, reflects 29 pharmacists \times 5 cases; $n = 22$ for ChatGPT-4.5 reflects 22 unique case numbers evaluated. *p*-values are calculated using Welch's *t*-test for unequal variances, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 8. Interrater reliability (Intraclass Correlation Coefficients) for pharmacists and ChatGPT-4.5 responses.

Group	ICC(2,1)	95% CI	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i> -value	ICC(2,4)	Interpretation
Pharmacists–Arabic	0.492	0.423–0.588	5.09	< 0.001	0.80	Good-Excellent
Pharmacists–English	0.466	0.31–0.603	2.07	< 0.001	0.76	Good-Excellent
Pharmacists–Overall	0.479	0.32–0.62	3.22	< 0.001	0.78	Good-Excellent
ChatGPT-4.5–English	0.66	0.50–0.83	9.55	< 0.001	0.89	Good-Excellent
ChatGPT-4.5–Arabic	0.59	0.40–0.78	7.13	< 0.001	0.85	Good-Excellent
ChatGPT-4.5–Overall	0.62	0.51–0.76	8.18	< 0.001	0.87	Good-Excellent

Note: ICC (2,1) represents the reliability of a single pharmacist rater, while ICC (2,4) reflects the reliability of the mean of four raters. *F*-statistics test whether the observed ICC differs significantly from zero; $p < 0.001$ in all cases indicates statistically significant interrater reliability. Interpretation of ICC values follows Koo and Li (2016): < 0.50 = poor, 0.50–0.75 = moderate, 0.75–0.90 = good, > 0.90 = excellent reliability.

($r = 0.376$, $p < 0.001$) but weak and non-significant in Arabic ($r = 0.147$, $p = 0.079$) (Fig. 1).

Inter-rater reliability

Two-way random-effects ICCs (absolute agreement) showed good single-rater reliability and excellent average-rater reliability overall for ChatGPT-4.5 responses and fair-to-moderate single-rater but good average-rater reliability for pharmacist responses. Overall: Pharmacists ICC(2,1) = 0.479; ICC(2,4) = 0.78. ChatGPT-4.5 ICC(2,1) = 0.62; ICC(2,4) = 0.87. Language-specific estimates were similar (Table 8).

Difficulty classification and CLEAR by difficulty

Across the 44 scenarios (22 English; 22 Arabic), five (22.7%) were Easy, 14 (63.6%) Moderate, and three (13.6%) Difficult (Table 9). ChatGPT-4.5 maintained near-ceiling performance across difficulty levels, while pharmacist scores declined with complexity—especially in difficult English cases (Table 10).

Table 9. Distribution of cases by difficulty category.

Difficulty	Cases (<i>n</i>)	% of total	Example conditions
Easy	5	22.7%	Constipation 3, 5; hemorrhoids 13; GERD 20; mouth ulcer 22
Moderate	14	63.6%	Constipation 1, 2, 4; diarrhea 6–8, 10–11; hemorrhoids 12, 15; GERD 18–19; N/V 16–17
Difficult	3	13.6%	Diarrhea 9; hemorrhoids 14; mouth ulcer 21

Table 10. Comparison of pharmacist and ChatGPT-4.5 CLEAR scores across difficulty levels.

Difficulty	Language	Pharmacists CLEAR	ChatGPT-4.5 CLEAR	<i>p</i> -value
Easy	Arabic	4.16 \pm 0.96	4.82 \pm 0.19	0.2
	English	3.8 \pm 0.75	4.91 \pm 0.12	0.031
Moderate	Arabic	3.55 \pm 0.9	4.78 \pm 0.29	0.034
	English	3.8 \pm 0.76	4.86 \pm 0.11	0.037
Difficult	Arabic	3.86 \pm 0.72	4.58 \pm 0.46	0.035
	English	3.44 \pm 0.82	4.65 \pm 0.23	0.025

Qualitative comparison of responses

In addition to the quantitative CLEAR and cosine similarity findings, qualitative comparison revealed consistent differences in structure, clinical reasoning, and communication style between pharmacists and ChatGPT-4.5. Across both English and Arabic cases, ChatGPT-4.5 generally produced more structured, guideline-aligned, and explanatory responses, often incorporating self-care advice, rationale, and follow-up guidance. Pharmacist responses were frequently clinically appropriate, particularly in identifying referral-worthy cases, but showed greater variability in length, completeness, and communication style.

In red-flag scenarios, both pharmacists and ChatGPT-4.5 consistently recognized the need for referral. However, ChatGPT-4.5 more often framed its recommendations with explanatory and patient-oriented language, whereas pharmacist responses tended to be briefer and more directive. Similar differences were observed in mild or self-limiting conditions, where ChatGPT-4.5 more consistently included supportive self-care advice and contextual explanation alongside product recommendation.

Figure 1. Scatterplots showing the relationship between cosine similarity and CLEAR ratings for ChatGPT-4.5. **A.** For English cases; **B.** For Arabic cases, and pharmacist-generated responses; **C.** In English; **D.** In Arabic. Each panel includes individual data points with a fitted regression line. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and associated p -value are displayed within each subplot.

Selected qualitative excerpts and comparative examples illustrating differences in structure, tone, and completeness between pharmacists and ChatGPT-4.5 are provided in Appendix 1, while a thematic coding summary of recurring patterns across all cases is presented in Appendix 2.

Overall, qualitative analysis revealed that ChatGPT-4.5 generated linguistically diverse yet clinically coherent advice that mirrored pharmacists' reasoning but demonstrated greater structure, completeness, and patient orientation. Pharmacists displayed valuable contextual and experiential judgment, particularly in recognizing cases that required medical referral, but their responses were more variable in length and depth. These qualitative insights complement the quantitative findings, showing that ChatGPT-4.5 consistently delivered clear, evidence-based, and empathetic counseling messages, while pharmacists contributed real-world contextual judgment and human sensitivity essential to patient care.

Discussion

This study provides one of the first systematic evaluations of ChatGPT-4.5, an advanced generative language model, against licensed community pharmacists in responding to over-the-counter (OTC) drug information scenarios presented in both Arabic and English. By integrating the CLEAR framework, cosine similarity, inter-rater reliability, and difficulty-based case profiling, this study provides a multifaceted assessment of response quality, variability, and linguistic robustness. The findings highlight both the transformative potential and critical limitations of large language models (LLMs) as clinical decision-support tools in pharmacy practice.

A central finding was the consistent superiority of ChatGPT-4.5 over pharmacists across all evaluation metrics, with mean CLEAR scores approaching 4.8/5 compared with 3.7–3.8/5 for pharmacists. This margin was particularly pronounced in the lack of false information and relevance domains, underscoring the model's ability to generate accurate, guideline-aligned, and context-appropriate responses. These observations mirror emerging evidence that GPT-4-class models surpass human clinicians in clarity and quality of medical advice. For example, Ayers et al. (2023) showed that patients preferred ChatGPT responses to physician messages nearly 80% of the time, citing higher accuracy and empathy. Triplett et al. (2025) similarly reported superior clarity in GPT-4 responses to drug information queries compared with hospital pharmacists.

Several mechanisms may explain this performance gap. Unlike humans, LLMs integrate massive knowledge bases and instantly synthesize content from multimodal biomedical corpora, enabling consistently complete and evidence-grounded outputs. Additionally, ChatGPT-4.5's architecture reduces "hallucinations" compared with prior models (Munir et al. 2024), explaining its near-perfect performance in the lack of false information domain—a

traditional weakness of earlier LLMs. In contrast, pharmacist performance likely reflects real-world challenges such as knowledge decay, variable familiarity with guidelines, and time constraints, all well-documented sources of heterogeneity in community practice (Johnson et al. 2022).

Importantly, ChatGPT-4.5 maintained stable performance across Arabic and English, with no significant difference in CLEAR scores between languages. This contrasts with earlier versions of GPT, which showed degraded performance in Arabic (Sallam et al. 2024a). The improvement likely reflects expanded multilingual pre-training data and refined tokenization in GPT-4.5, allowing the model to capture domain-specific semantics beyond English.

Interestingly, the cosine similarity between pharmacist and ChatGPT responses was low overall (~0.08), particularly in Arabic (~0.04), despite ChatGPT's higher CLEAR scores. This finding indicates that superior quality was not the result of textual imitation. Rather, ChatGPT generated responses that were structurally and lexically distinct yet richer and more comprehensive—a desirable feature if AI tools are to augment rather than echo human reasoning. The stronger correlation between cosine similarity and pharmacist performance in English ($r = 0.376$) suggests that when pharmacists used structured, guideline-aligned phrasing, their quality improved—a signal that *language structure itself* may serve as a surrogate for response quality in human practice.

Case-level analyses revealed that pharmacist performance declined sharply with increasing difficulty, whereas ChatGPT-4.5 remained robust even in complex scenarios. This resilience aligns with prior findings in medical education, where GPT-4 maintained strong performance across Bloom's taxonomy in microbiology and clinical chemistry tasks (Salama 2024; Sallam et al. 2024b). The likely explanation is that LLMs excel at structured reasoning and retrieval-based tasks, whereas pharmacists may struggle when scenarios require higher-order synthesis, nuanced safety judgments, or referral decisions—areas where cognitive load and experiential variability play a larger role.

The safety profile findings reinforce this interpretation. Pharmacists produced unsafe recommendations in certain case types, such as diarrhea and mouth ulcers, whereas ChatGPT-4.5 produced none. This suggests that AI-driven tools could serve as a first-line safety net in OTC counseling, flagging potential risks or omissions before patient harm occurs. However, it also underscores the importance of human oversight: while AI excels at recall and guideline application, it remains limited in interpreting ambiguous histories or nonverbal cues—core components of real-world consultations.

Beyond comparative performance, the integration of AI into OTC counseling raises important ethical, legal, and implementation issues. Liability remains uncertain when AI-generated recommendations are incomplete, inappropriate, or fail to identify referral-worthy red flags, particularly if such outputs contribute to delayed care or patient harm. There is also a practical risk of overreliance,

whereby patients or pharmacists may defer excessively to AI-generated advice at the expense of individualized clinical judgment. Moreover, safe implementation in community pharmacy will require explicit regulatory frameworks addressing model validation, transparency, auditability, documentation, and data governance, as well as clear boundaries for acceptable use. Taken together, these considerations support the role of AI as a supervised adjunct to pharmacist counseling rather than a replacement for professional responsibility.

Notably, pharmacist performance varied across gastrointestinal domains, with relatively higher scores in nausea and vomiting scenarios compared with diarrhea or constipation. This variation may reflect differences in familiarity and confidence linked to clinical exposure. Nausea and vomiting are common presentations in pregnancy, medication side effects, and viral illness—conditions pharmacists frequently encounter and manage using well-established OTC recommendations. Conversely, diarrhea cases, particularly those involving dehydration or blood in stool, demand greater diagnostic discrimination and carry higher perceived risk. In such instances, pharmacists tended to adopt a defensive approach, providing minimal advice or immediate referral without detailed self-care recommendations. This cautiousness likely stems from uncertainty in differentiating infectious from noninfectious etiologies and limited access to stool testing or patient follow-up in community settings. These findings suggest that domain-specific comfort and perceived liability strongly influence pharmacists' counseling depth, underscoring the need for targeted training in triage and red-flag recognition.

The demographic analysis revealed a negative correlation between pharmacist age and CLEAR performance ($r = -0.33$), indicating that younger pharmacists outperformed older counterparts. This pattern echoes findings by Abu Farha et al. (2014), who reported declining evidence-based knowledge with increasing years of practice. The result suggests that recency of training and digital literacy may significantly shape pharmacists' ability to deliver comprehensive drug information. Addressing these gaps will require targeted continuing education and decision-support tools integrated into pharmacy workflows.

Beyond age, other demographic variables—including shift time, pharmacy type, and practice location—showed no significant association with performance, suggesting that systemic factors may play a larger role than individual practice contexts.

The implications of these findings for clinical pharmacy practice and digital health integration are considerable. ChatGPT-4.5's consistent performance across languages and case complexity suggests that it may serve as a valuable decision-support tool in community pharmacy settings. When integrated into dispensing systems or counseling workflows, such tools may help standardize counseling quality and reduce inter-pharmacist variability, allowing pharmacists to focus on complex or ambiguous cases requiring clinical judgment.

In education, ChatGPT-4.5-generated responses may also serve as benchmark exemplars aligned with CLEAR domains to guide pharmacist training and communication skills development. From a policy perspective, these findings also emphasize the need for governance frameworks that ensure accountability, transparency, and safety in the deployment of AI tools in clinical settings. Fine-tuning models on locally relevant Arabic-language data may further enhance cultural and linguistic alignment.

Study limitations

This study's findings should be interpreted considering several limitations. The sample size ($n = 58$) was modest and geographically concentrated in Amman, limiting generalizability. The case set was restricted to gastrointestinal conditions, and some case types (e.g., mouth ulcers) were underrepresented. In addition, the case-difficulty classification was derived from a small pilot group of five pharmacists and was intended only for preliminary stratification. As such, some misclassification or instability in difficulty categorization is possible, and findings by difficulty level should be interpreted cautiously. Simulated written cases standardize comparisons but do not capture the complexity of real patient (real-time) interactions, including nonverbal communication and evolving clinical narratives.

Despite the use of forward-back translation to ensure linguistic equivalence, subtle differences in meaning or tone may have been lost in the Arabic cases. While inter-rater reliability among evaluators was high, some subjectivity in CLEAR scoring remains inevitable given the qualitative nature of judgment involved. In addition, because each pharmacist provided five case responses, the data included clustered observations nested within participants. Although participant-level averaging yielded patterns comparable to the response-level analyses, formal multilevel or cluster-adjusted modeling was not applied; therefore, the inferential estimates may be somewhat overprecise. The ChatGPT-4.5 arm also included only twenty-two responses per language (one per case), whereas the pharmacist arm contained multiple participant-generated responses for each scenario. This imbalance reduced observable variability in the AI arm and may have made ChatGPT-4.5 performance appear more stable than would be expected under repeated generations or alternative prompting conditions. Accordingly, direct statistical comparisons between the two arms should be interpreted with caution. Finally, results reflect the capabilities of ChatGPT-4.5 at a specific time point, and future model iterations may perform differently.

Future research should include larger, multicenter samples; apply multilevel modeling to account for repeated measures; and incorporate interactive, real-world simulations to capture the dynamic nature of pharmacist-patient communication.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that ChatGPT-4.5 can consistently generate high-quality, safe, and contextually appropriate OTC counseling responses that exceed those of community pharmacists across two languages and multiple case types. Its performance remains strong across difficulty levels and is unaffected by language, highlighting the maturity of modern LLMs for clinical decision-support roles. At the same time, the variability and demographic influences observed among pharmacists underscore ongoing challenges in human performance. Rather than replacing pharmacists, these findings point toward synergistic, copilot models, in which AI augments routine decision-making under appropriate professional oversight, while pharmacists provide clinical judgment, patient engagement, and nuanced interpretation—a direction aligned with the evolving landscape of digital pharmacy practice.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Applied Science Private University (Approval No. 2025-PHA-16). All participants provided informed consent, and the study followed the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following:

This paper was about AI in general, and ChatGPT was used as part of the study methodology. In addition for language checking and paraphrasing.

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Author contributions

Ala'a Al-Safadi contributed to data collection, methodology development, data curation, formal analysis, and drafting the initial manuscript. Wala'a Al-Safadi participated in data collection, methodology development, and manuscript review. Amal Akour supervised the methodological design, validated analytical procedures, and contributed to manuscript editing. Rana Abu Farha assisted with data acquisition, interpretation of findings, and critical review. Raja'a A. Al-Qudah contributed to manuscript revision. Souheil Hallit revised the manuscript. Mohammed Sallam supported conceptualization, interpretation of results, and manuscript editing. Muna Barakat conceived and supervised the study, led the writing process, coordinated all manuscript revisions, and approved the final version as the corresponding author.

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Data availability

The datasets generated and analyzed during the study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Appendix 1

Table A1. Sample comparative responses between pharmacists and ChatGPT-4.5.

Case (condition)	Pharmacist response (representative example)	ChatGPT-4.5 response	Comment/thematic observation
Constipation (19-year-old student, poor diet and inactivity)	“Advise fiber and fluids, maybe use a laxative.”	“Increase fiber intake, fluids, and regular exercise. If needed, use polyethylene glycol 3350 or a glycerin suppository for short-term relief.”	ChatGPT-4.5 provided a structured, evidence-based plan that integrated lifestyle and pharmacological guidance, while pharmacist advice was brief and less specific.
Diarrhea with blood and dizziness (red-flag case)	“Refer to doctor immediately.”	“The presence of blood and mucus in stool may indicate infection or inflammatory bowel disease. Please visit a healthcare provider immediately to prevent dehydration and complications.”	Both recognized the need for referral; ChatGPT-4.5 added explanatory rationale and patient reassurance.
GERD (recurrent heartburn, 36-year-old female)	“Use omeprazole once daily; avoid spicy food.”	“Avoid large or fatty meals, remain upright after eating, and consider omeprazole if symptoms occur more than twice per week.”	Pharmacist focused on medication only; ChatGPT-4.5 integrated behavioral modifications and appropriate OTC use threshold.
Mouth ulcer (13-year-old boy)	“Hydrocortisone pellets, twice daily.”	“This appears to be a minor aphthous ulcer. Maintain oral hygiene, avoid spicy foods, and use hydrocortisone buccal pellets if pain persists.”	ChatGPT-4.5 demonstrated higher completeness by adding cause explanation and self-care advice.
Hemorrhoids (pregnant woman, Arabic case)	استخدمي كريم البواسير واشربي سوائل	“أنصح باستخدام مرهم موضعي يحتوي على مواد واقية مثل أكسيد الزنك مع الجلوس في حمام دافئ يوماً ثلاث مرات، وزيادة شرب الماء وتناول الألياف.”	Both provided appropriate therapy, but ChatGPT-4.5 gave more detailed lifestyle and procedural recommendations, showing greater educational depth.
Diarrhea in child (Arabic case)	“راقبي الطفل، أعطيه سوائل، وراجعي الطبيب إذا استمر الإسهال.”	“يبدو أن الطفل يعاني من إسهال حاد بعد تناول طعام ملوث. يجب إعطاؤه محاليل الإماهة الفموية بكميات صغيرة بشكل متكرر، وإذا لم يتحسن خلال ٤٢ ساعة راجعي الطبيب.”	ChatGPT-4.5 provided a clearer cause-based explanation and step-wise management advice.

Appendix 2

Table A2. Thematic coding summary of qualitative comparison between pharmacists and ChatGPT-4.5 responses.

Theme	Description	Representative evidence (quotes)	Frequency across cases (n = 22)	Observed trend
1. Structure and organization	Logical flow of assessment → recommendation → follow-up.	ChatGPT-4.5: “Increase fiber intake, fluids, and regular exercise. If needed, use polyethylene glycol 3350 or a glycerin suppository for short-term relief.” Pharmacist: “Use laxative and drink water.”	21 cases	ChatGPT-4.5 demonstrated consistently structured outputs; pharmacist responses varied widely in format.
2. Clinical accuracy and safety	Identification of red flags and correct referral decisions.	Pharmacist: “Refer to doctor immediately—possible infection.” ChatGPT-4.5: “The presence of blood in stool suggests infection or inflammation; seek immediate medical care.”	22 cases	Both groups showed strong safety awareness, but ChatGPT-4.5 added context and reasoning.
3. Completeness and depth of counseling	Inclusion of pharmacologic + non-pharmacologic advice and follow-up.	ChatGPT-4.5: “Avoid fatty meals, remain upright after eating, and use omeprazole if symptoms persist.” Pharmacist: “Use omeprazole once daily.”	19 cases	ChatGPT-4.5 provided multi-dimensional guidance; pharmacists often focused on drug choice only.
4. Patient education and explanation	Provision of rationale, mechanism, or prevention information.	ChatGPT-4.5: “ORS helps replace lost electrolytes; dehydration can worsen fatigue.” Pharmacist: “Administer ORS if diarrhea continues.”	17 cases	ChatGPT-4.5 offered explanatory context, improving educational value and clarity.
5. Tone and empathy	Degree of reassurance, politeness, and patient-centered language.	ChatGPT-4.5 (Arabic): “من الأفضل مراجعة الطبيب للتأكد من سلامتك، واحرص على شرب كميات كافية من السوائل.” Pharmacist: “راجع الطبيب فوراً.”	20 cases	ChatGPT-4.5 maintained a courteous, empathetic tone; pharmacists used more directive phrasing.
6. Language quality and bilingual consistency	Grammar, coherence, and cultural appropriateness in English/Arabic.	ChatGPT-4.5: produced grammatically accurate, fluent responses in both languages.	22 cases	ChatGPT-4.5 showed stable bilingual performance; pharmacists' Arabic responses occasionally contained typographical or grammatical errors.
7. Variability across cases	Range of response quality within each group.	NA (evaluated at case level).	—	Pharmacists' responses showed higher variability; ChatGPT-4.5 maintained consistent output quality.